

Sustainability Plan

Deliverable D7.8

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About this document

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

The European Centre of Excellence in Weather and Climate in Europe (ESIWACE) is an activity that has been funded by the European Commission since 2016 under the HPC Centre of Excellence (CoE) programme with two subsequent projects, ESIWACE and ESIWACE2, aiming to develop and promote exascale-ready weather and climate codes, address skills gaps, and bring together the community working on these problems.

ESIWACE2 terminates at the end of 2022. However, there are ongoing requirements, which are diverse, and range from specific technology objectives to ensuring that there are ongoing mechanisms of formal and informal collaboration. It will remain important for the European weather and climate science community to work together on developing and evolving codes, infrastructure and services suitable for the exascale era. In this context, the European community includes the full spectrum of existing partners, including those who are partners in the ECMWF who are not parties to all of Digital Europe or Horizon Europe funding.

The community intends to build on other initiatives to establish a self-funded coordination entity whose remit will include delivering on a set of their requirements. However, it remains the case that project funding (both national and from the European Commission) will be indispensable to deliver the scientific and technical progress necessary to fulfil the aspirations of society to exploit exascale (and post-exascale) computing to provide the weather and climate information that our society urgently needs.

2. Conclusion & Results

There is a set of requirements in the field of using high performance computing for weather and climate simulations, which need to be addressed in an ongoing and sustained way. These needs apply to code evolution and code development, dealing with the data deluge, and coordination of joint working in this complex field. The expectation of the community is that most of the requirements identified above will continue to be delivered by projects, targeting specific actions that encompass a group of the requirements, but that no single project will deliver them all. However, a truly sustainable infrastructure should not depend only on project funding based on short-term decisions, opportunities, and restrictions.

ESIWACE is therefore contributing to activities targeted to sustain at least a significant subset of the necessary activities independently of short-term funding opportunities. This includes a) the attempt to the European Network for Earth System modelling (ENES) to create a legacy entity to be funded by partner contributions, which will provide high level coordination of projects, b) the planned procurements of Destination Earth and c) the planned update of the ENES infrastructure strategy.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of the following macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	X

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	X
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	X
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	X
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	X

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

Based on extensive discussions within the community and on external developments like the publication of EU calls and the ending and advent of related projects, a memo has been written to assess the current situation and landscape and possible midterm and longer-term actions.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

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6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

The deliverable is being published two months later than planned to be able to take into account the EuroHPC JU calls impacting directly on our short- and medium-term planning. The fact that a) the scope of these calls changed from the previous calls in addressing the activities of our single

project in two separate new calls and b) important partners of the project are being ruled out for funding by these calls made an adoption of the short- and medium-term planning necessary.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

The deliverable addresses the Strategy for HPC of the Weather and Climate community, which is a key user of the European HPC ecosystem.

8. Sustainability

Sustainability and links with other projects is the topic of this deliverable and is discussed in the memo attached to this document.

9. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The document will be circulated within the community and presented in particular to the groups dealing with a putative ENES-RI and the ENES strategic foresight.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Please note: for completeness we added some events which took place after the date of delivery in this revision of the document.

Type of activities	Details	Date & location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo record link / link to website	Est. no. of persons reached
Participation to a workshop	Joachim Biercamp (DKRZ), "Link to ESIWACE-2", 1st ESCAPE-2 Dissemination Workshop	21-22 October 2019, Reading (UK)	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/3948035	60
Participation to a workshop	Rupert Ford (STFC), "PSyclone, LFRic, NEMO and SIR",	21-22 October 2019, Reading	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/3972115	60

Type of activities	Details	Date & location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo record link / link to website	Est. no. of persons reached
	1st ESCAPE-2 Dissemination Workshop	(UK)			
Organisation of a workshop	Virtual workshop on "New Opportunities for ML/AI in Weather and Climate Modelling" Organized by Graham Riley, Giovanni Aloisio and others.	16-18 March 2021, online	Scientific Community/Industry	https://is.enes.org/workshops-detailed/#ML-AI-WS	290
Participation to a workshop	Donatello Elia, presentation "Ophidia: High Performance Data Analytics framework for Climate Change at scale" at the IS-ENES3 Virtual workshop on requirements for a fast and scalable evaluation workflow, 18-19 May 2021	19 May 2021, online	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/5535705	30
Participation to a conference	Sylvie Joussaume, "Modelling Climate Change", keynote presentation at the EuroHPC Summit Week 2022 / PRACEdays22	22-24 March 2022, Paris (FR)	Scientific community, Industry	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6394412	300
Participation to a conference	Gijs van den Oord, roundtable discussion participation on	22-24 March 2022, Paris (FR)	Scientific community, Industry	n/a	30

Type of activities	Details	Date & location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo record link / link to website	Est. no. of persons reached
	"Serving complementarity of application needs throughout the HPC Pyramid", chaired by Edouard Audit at the EuroHPC Summit Week 2022 / PRACEdays22				
Participation to a conference	Miguel Castrillo, presentation "The new very-high-resolution coupled global configuration for EC-Earth 4" at the EuroHPC Summit Week 2022 / PRACEdays22	22-24 March 2022, Paris (FR)	Scientific community, Industry	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6491778	20
Organisation of a workshop	7th ENES HPC Workshop, co-organized with the IS-ENES3 project	9-11 May 2022, Barcelona (ES)	Scientific community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/7th-enes-hpc-workshop	130
Selected talks at the 7th ENES HPC Workshop					
	Eric Maisonnave, 7th ENES HPC Workshop, Barcelona: The new load balancing tool in OASIS3-MCT_5.0	9-11 May 2022, Barcelona (ES)	Scientific community	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/IS-ENES3/IS-ENES-Portal-Website/master/pdf_documents/CW7_session3_Maisonnave.pdf	130
	Sam Hatfield, 7th ENES HPC Workshop, Barcelona: ARMing the IFS: Experiments and experiences from porting the ECMWF model to Fugaku	9-11 May 2022, Barcelona (ES)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/record/6805913	130

Type of activities	Details	Date & location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo record link / link to website	Est. no. of persons reached
	Donatello Elia, 7th ENES HPC Workshop, Barcelona: Towards HPC and Big Data convergence for climate analysis at scale	9-11 May 2022, Barcelona (ES)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/record/6783441	80
	Peter Dueben (ECMWF), 7th ENES HPC Workshop, Barcelona: Machine learning for weather and climate predictions	9-11 May 2022, Barcelona (ES)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/record/6792121-.YsGjoi8RrmE	130
	Italo Epicoco (CMCC), 7th ENES HPC Workshop, Barcelona: Performance optimization in NEMO ocean model	9-11 May 2022, Barcelona (ES)	Scientific community	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/IS-ENES3/IS-ENES-Portal-Website/master/pdf_documents/CW7_session3_Epicoco.pdf	130
	Iva Kavcic (UK MetO), 7th ENES HPC Workshop, Barcelona: PSyclone in Met Office: Evolution and revolution	9-11 May 2022, Barcelona (ES)	Scientific community	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/IS-ENES3/IS-ENES-Portal-Website/master/pdf_documents/CW7_session4_Kavcic.pdf	130
	Gijs van den Oord, 7th ENES HPC Workshop, Barcelona: Accelerating tracer transport in FESOM-2 with GPU's	9-11 May 2022, Barcelona (ES)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/record/6552990	80
	Reinhard Budich (MPI-M), 7th	9-11 May 2022,	Scientific community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6806923	130

Type of activities	Details	Date & location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo record link / link to website	Est. no. of persons reached
	ENES HPC Workshop, Barcelona: On the Potential of Concurrency for Scaling W&C Applications in the ExaSCALE Era	Barcelona/ Online			
Participation in a workshop	Florian Ziemer (DKRZ), participation in data support team at NextGEMS Cycle 2 Hackathon; ESIWACE2 support via DYAMOND compute time resources and funding for Hackathon location	June 28 - July 2, 2022, Vienna (AT)	Scientific community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/nextgems-2nd-cycle-hackathon	80

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

- Bryan Lawrence (UREAD-NCAS), Fanny Adloff (DKRZ), and Sylvie Jousaume (CNRS-IPSL): Infrastructure Strategy for Earth System Modelling for 2024-2033: What is needed to sustain large-scale European earth system modelling infrastructure from 2024 and beyond, IS-ENES3 Deliverable D2.1, in preparation (to be published in May 2023)
- Lawrence, Bryan, Adloff, Fanny, André, Jean-Claude, Biercamp, Joachim, Fladrich, Uwe, Hines, Adrian, Jousaume, Sylvie, Juckes, Martin, Serradell, Kim, & Valcke, Sophie. (2022). European objectives for Models, Tools and HPC in the future research infrastructure. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6807389>

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

n/a

Annex to Deliverable 7.8: The future of ESIWACE

By Bryan Lawrence and Joachim Biercamp, February 2022

Summary

The European Centre of Excellence in Weather and Climate in Europe (ESIWACE) is an activity that has been funded by the European Commission since 2016 under the HPC Centre of Excellence (CoE) programme with two subsequent projects, ESIWACE and ESIWACE2, aiming to develop and promote exascale-ready weather and climate codes, address skills gaps, and bring together the community working on these problems.

ESIWACE2 terminates at the end of 2022.

This document describes the issues around sustaining the requirements of the ESIWACE community as they present themselves in February 2022 (the contractual delivery date for this document).

As of January 2022, there are two calls available to support the continuation of ESIWACE activities, but the expected scope of our response cannot fully address the requirements of the community. There is too much work for any single funding line, the expected scope of the calls limits what can be proposed and in addition, there are eligibility issues.

The ongoing requirements are diverse, and range from specific technology objectives, to ensuring that there are ongoing mechanisms of formal and informal collaboration. It will remain important for the European weather and climate science community to work together on developing and evolving codes suitable for the exascale era.

In this context, the European community includes the full spectrum of existing partners, including those who are partners in the ECMWF who are not parties to all of Digital Europe or Horizon Europe funding.

The community intends to build on other initiatives to establish a self-funded coordination entity whose remit will include delivering on a set of their requirements. However, it remains the case that project funding (both national and from the European Commission) will be indispensable to deliver the scientific and technical progress necessary to fulfil the aspirations of society to exploit exascale (and post-exascale) computing to provide the weather and climate information that our society urgently needs.

Introduction

The European Centre of Excellence in Weather and Climate in Europe (ESIWACE) is an HPC Centre of Excellence¹, one of fifteen CoEs currently funded. An initial phase² of the centre's activity was funded from 2015 until 2019, the current phase ESIWACE2³ is funded until the end of 2022.

¹ <https://www.hpccoe.eu/eu-hpc-centres-of-excellence2/>

² <https://www.esiwace.eu/the-project/hpc-landscape/esiwace-1>

³ <https://www.esiwace.eu/the-project/hpc-landscape/esiwace2>

The current strap line for the activities is:

1. To promote the use of upcoming exascale and extreme performance computing capabilities and scale up existing parallel codes towards exascale scaling performance.
2. To address the skills gap in computational science in the targeted domains by specialised training for increased adoption of advanced HPC in industry and academia.
3. To bring together the European world-class knowledge and expertise in applying established mechanisms, user-driven development, performance tools and programming models for HPC, and co-design activities for real systems based on leading edge technologies.

The current CoE programme is ending soon, and as noted above, the existing ESIWACE2 funding concludes at the end of calendar year 2022. The EC is continuing with HPC centres of excellence via two calls published very recently, end of January 2022, with closing dates in April 2022:

CALL 1: *Advancing Lighthouse Exascale Applications*⁴ to develop or scale up existing parallel codes towards exascale performance, resulting into tangible benefits mainly for scientific challenges.

As of February 2022, it is thought very unlikely that the ESIWACE community will submit a bid under this call.

- The first phase of ESIWACE already demonstrated that several European Weather and Climate Models can be scaled up towards exascale performance and the current project, ESIWACE2, delivered prototypes of codes suitable for real scientific use cases. These models are already being used and extended with the aspiration to deliver tangible benefits mainly for scientific and societal challenges within large international projects. A prominent example for such a new activity is the EU-funded NextGEMS project⁵, which is driven by ESIWACE partners, and is cooperating with ESIWACE2 via the DYAMOND initiative. NextGEMS is deploying two of the ESIWACE2 flagship models, namely the ECMWF model IFS and the German ICON model for scientific research. In a way of speaking, the ESIWACE and ESIWACE2 projects were very successful in delivering what is sought by EuroHPC JU and targeted in this new call.
- The DestinE⁶ programme co-led by ESIWACE partner ECMWF (which is a follow-up to the ExtremeEarth initiative addressed in the ESIWACE2 proposal as being central for the sustainability planning) is preparing to procure a Digital Twin of the Earth to assess climate extremes. It is expected that some ESIWACE partners will contribute to bids for this large-scale procurement, building on and, if successful, continuing the development of ESIWACE flagship codes.
- A number of partners that are leading in the development of weather and climate models in Europe are, as of today, not eligible to bid for this call. Therefore, for example, the models of the UK Met Office, which certainly have the potential to be additional Lighthouse Exascale Applications, could not be considered for funding in this call.

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-eurohpc-ju-2021-coe-01-01>

⁵ <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>

⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/destination-earth>

CALL 2: *Advancing the transition towards exascale capabilities*⁷ by developing or scaling up existing parallel codes, resulting into effective applications to solve scientific, industrial or societal challenges and addressing the needs of the user communities.

The ESIWACE community is currently organising itself to bid to this second call as discussed below. However, there are two caveats, which reduce flexibility and possible scope for this bid.

- Neither call allows the participation of the United Kingdom or Switzerland. There are significant ESIWACE community activities, which are led from, or predominantly carried out in the UK and Switzerland. These cannot be continued using these calls and workarounds are still under discussion.
- The call expects 50% national funding. There are worries about the flexibility of national funding in some partners, which might make it difficult for all activities to be appropriately funded.

The key questions then become:

- What are the aspirations of the ESIWACE Community for the ongoing evolution of ESIWACE, within or outside of the continuation programme?
- How might they be met?

This document attempts to lay out some of the choices, in the context of existing activities, both within the current ESIWACE programme, and expected to be carried out with other funding. There are four sections: a short restatement of current ESIWACE activities, list of related activities, a list of ongoing requirements, and a set of aspirations as to how those requirements might be delivered.

What is ESIWACE now?

The overall goals of the existing project are to

1. "Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021."
2. "Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available."

The work is divided into six core objectives and six non-management work packages, all of which pan multiple objectives. Below we list these objectives as formulated in the ESIWACE2 description of action, followed (in italics) by a short summary of the underlying motivation and methodology:

1. Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms.
Improve throughput and scalability of leading European weather and climate models and demonstrate the technical and scientific performance of the models in unprecedented resolution on pre- exascale EuroHPC systems. (WP1)

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-eurohpc-ju-2021-coe-01-02>

This is about actually getting production runs going on large systems, doing "hero-runs", and enabling other projects to exploit the capabilities developed in ESIWACE (e.g. DYAMOND).

2. Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling.
Develop and establish domain-specific languages (DSLs) for community models and to evaluate the potential of innovative technologies such as machine learning to explore new methodologies in Earth system modelling. (WP2)
The main objective here is to get experience in the community of working with emerging technologies (such as containers and the use of machine learning to emulate parts of simulation code), as well as to share information on, and expand the usage of, two different domain specific languages for weather and climate developed within the ESIWACE community.
3. Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community.
Provide support and training to the community to profile and optimise code performance (WP6), and to port models to existing and upcoming exascale supercomputers. (WP3)
The WP3 goal is a mix of delivering software for benchmarking (to help vendors support the community) and to provide software support to the community via open calls which provide resources to solve specific problems. The WP6 goal is to deliver training and networking opportunities via community workshops, summer schools, and targeted training workshops.
4. Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale
Develop tools to mitigate the effects of the data deluge from high-resolution simulation: ensemble tools to minimise data output, storage middleware to handle IO performance, and improved tools for post-processing data analytics and visualisation. (WP4, WP5)
This is primarily about developing data management software, I/O middleware and ensemble tools and about integrating visualisation and analytics with each other and the I/O middleware.
5. Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem
Reach out to the European HPC initiatives, in particular to related FET projects, to PRACE and to EuroHPC and provide platforms for dedicated interactions between the climate and weather community and the HPC stakeholders. (WP6)
In addition to the training and networking objectives discussed above in terms of "enhancing capacity", WP6 aims to deliver active and regular coordination of community aspirations, and proactive engagement with other key players in the European HPC ecosystem (institutions, vendors, and other consortia and disciplines).
6. Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres
Co-design in particular supported through the High-Performance Climate and Weather benchmark (HPCW; WP3) but also by all of the above. (all WPs)
A key thread of all the activities in ESIWACE is to engage the four quadrants of the community (users, developers, institutions, vendors) in finding solutions to next generation computing requirements.

What are the ongoing requirements?

Code Evolution and Code Development: While one or two existing codes might be exascale-ready, or funded to become exascale ready, it remains likely that the science requires multiple exascale-ready codes (particularly in order to address structural uncertainty in climate). Hence, it will not be sufficient for weather and climate science for only one or two lighthouse applications. Most large modelling groups also recognise that even their latest re-tooling to become exascale-ready will struggle to deliver the necessary speed improvements to fully exploit exascale (and post-exascale) platforms, and meet science goals (Schulthess et al 2018). To address these issues, activities which continue to push code evolution across the community, and which support the development of new codes, are required (Lawrence et al 2018, Bauer et al 2021).

To address these it is necessary:

1. For the community to access suitable **training** to help make codes *performant* on exascale machines, *portable* across machines, and to remain scientifically *productive* (accessible to, and modifiable by, scientists).
2. To support the **development and exploitation of new software techniques** such as the Domain Specific Languages which are likely to address the requirement of simultaneously addressing performance, portability, and productivity, which are otherwise all unlikely to be easily achieved in any one code.
3. To provide **research services** which allow the expertise of one group (on say code performance) to be delivered to other groups, enabling faster and more efficient transformation of codes towards exascale and (beyond).
4. To support the **development of numerical methods** which might deliver alternative methods of solving the necessary equations (e.g. new mathematics, more use of machine learning), and in all the new developments.
5. To foster the joint **co-design** by industry and the scientific community of new codes (and workflows).
6. To sustain the information transfer between scientists, software engineers and industry, within and between institutions. This will involve ongoing **coordination** of *networking*, *workshops*, and other mechanisms of informal and formal information transfer.

Mitigating and avoiding the data deluge: It is well known that weather and climate applications produce vast amounts of data, and that the data produced scales (in some way) with the available compute resources. Handling such data is problematic at scale, and the financial and energetic costs are significant. The amount of that extra data expected as applications progress to exascale will depend on a complex interplay of human behaviour: what data is saved, whether it is compressed, and whether or not re-computation is envisaged as an alternative to saving, and how the computing resources are used (if on resolution alone, the data increase will be less than if it is used on ensemble-size alone, and that choice is influenced by both scientific requirements and code capabilities). Data flow and making choices about whether data should be saved will depend

on good tooling, much of which is as yet immature, as the requisite level of tooling was not needed pre-petascale. It is necessary that:

Tools must be developed and improved to *simplify workflows at scale*, to *analyse and visualise data as it is produced*, and to *manage deep storage efficiently*. These tools will need to include:

1. **I/O-servers** and other tools which handle the efficient migration of data between compute nodes and storage.
2. **Workflow tools** for managing the data flow between job phases, across storage tiers, and across Wide Area Networks.
3. **Methods for making more use of compression and direct analysis**. The more data can be compressed, or that storing it can be avoided by "in-flight" analysis and visualisation", the more the data deluge is mitigated.
4. **Enhanced Information Systems**. The more that data can be stored at rest, with no energy costs for storage, and only for retrieval and use, the better. But efficiently managing exabytes of data which is at rest requires complex information systems, optimised for handling weather and climate data. This is difficult in a dedicated centre such as ECMWF or DKRZ, but even more difficult when multiple sites are involved (e.g. simulations running as part of a coordinated experiment across multiple EuroHPC platforms).

Joint Working: It is generally agreed that no one group or centre has the requisite knowledge to make all the necessary advances, and that the introduction of software dependences between groups requires changes in behaviour by both producers and consumers of such software (Lawrence et al, 2018). It is also the case that large expensive simulations will need to be shared by scientific communities who will have to come together to define the necessary numerical experiments (Pascoe et al, 2020) and share the data produced, possibly via new and innovative mechanisms (Bauer et al, 2021). Addressing joint working will involve:

1. **Coordinated requirements gathering and architecting** both of software systems and numerical experiments.
2. Supplementing the information transfers necessary for code development and evolution with **formal effort sharing** around key components and software utilities.
3. **Training courses** and **summer schools** which provide **formal education** on tools and techniques.
4. **Clarity in development and support costs** particularly where large groups share code development.

Delivering: Sustaining the ESiWACE requirements

The expectation of the community is that most of the requirements identified above will continue to be delivered by projects, targeting specific actions that encompass a group of the requirements, but that no single project will deliver them all - including a potential continuation of ESiWACE under one of the currently open calls. An ESiWACE3 proposal will be submitted for an ongoing HPC CoE under the "Advancing the transition towards exascale" call.

The proposal is being shaped as this document is being finalised, but the following boundary conditions with respect to the scope of the project are already clear:

- It will not include work on advancing the weather and climate simulation models themselves towards exascale. The most prominent models are already quite advanced with respect to exascale readiness and further deployment and developments will be funded by other projects or national initiatives. The potential added benefit that is offered by the available EuroHPC calls is comparatively small and we deem it wiser to use the limited funding opportunity to help transferring expertise from these larger projects to the community. In addition some of the groups owning or co-developing central Weather and Climate codes are not eligible for funding by EuroHPC JU (Switzerland, UK).
- It will not be able to directly fund work on Domain Specific Languages, as the leaders of those activities are in the UK and Switzerland and are currently ruled out of these calls. Ways are sought to nevertheless sustain the close collaboration of ESIWACE with these groups. The ESIWACE2 partners from UK and Switzerland are currently probing options to obtain some national funding to continue interacting with the ESIWACE community for the mutual benefit.
- It will not include continuation of a significant amount of the work on data handling carried out in ESIWACE2, as that would require UK participation.
- It should be pointed out that the last two activities are crucial to European Commission Digital Environment goals of exploiting exascale computing in service of society.

In addition to these restrictions, it is clear that for reasons of scale it will be impossible to fund all the requirements, which are in scope: hence there will remain a need for other projects addressing the same broad set of requirements.

A truly sustainable infrastructure should of course not depend on project funding based on short-term decisions, opportunities and restrictions. The question has been considered if the ESIWACE community should attempt to create a new sustainable entity funded by partner contributions (or directly from nation states) which could also contribute to those requirements or help coordinate the necessary projects.

Leaving aside the creation of an entity on a very large scale and with a specific mission (e.g. a new international climate centre), we currently believe that an attempt to establish a generic ESIWACE entity is not useful because it would replicate other activities:

1. The existing ESIWACE2 project is delivered within a portfolio of projects loosely coordinated by the European Network for Earth System modelling (ENES⁸). ESIWACE2 was a complementary project with IS-ENES3 (with many of the same partners, serving the same scientific community, running at the same time for the same duration, albeit with different objectives and activities), however there will not be an EC-funded IS-ENES4. As a consequence, IS-ENES3 is attempting to leave a legacy entity to be funded by partner contributions, which will provide high level coordination of projects aimed at delivering ENES requirements and starting work in 2023 or beyond.

⁸ <https://portal.enes.org/>

- The scope, size, legal status and business model of the new entity are under active discussion, with ESiWACE fully engaged. As a consequence, it is not currently expected that there is any value in developing another entity with similar aims, as the ESiWACE aims will be included within the purview of the new entity.
 - It is unlikely that the new entity will be fully established and functional at the beginning of 2023, nor that at inception it will be able to fully fund all its activities, even those which are just coordination, and so funding from projects to support it will be expected. As a consequence, we expect the ESiWACE3 bid to include a component of support for the new entity, and for many of the funded activities within ESiWACE3 to be consistent with the wider community objectives outlined in that entity's terms of reference.
2. Destination Earth (DestinE)⁹ is expected to procure in the very near future two digital twins of the Earth, which will address several (but not all) of the ESiWACE requirements and build on some of the ESiWACE work.
 3. The ENES community is preparing for a new update of its infrastructure strategy^{10 11} with a kick-off meeting in March 2022. This strategy update will collect and sharpen community requirements including those addressed by the ESiWACE projects.

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⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/destination-earth>

¹⁰ Mitchell J., Budich R., Joussaume S., Lawrence B. and Marotzke J. (2012), Infrastructure strategy for the European Earth System Modelling community 2012-2022, ENES Report Series 1,

¹¹ Joussaume S., Lawrence B. and Guglielmo F. (2017), Update of the ENES infrastructure strategy 2012-2022, ENES Report Series 2, 20 pp